

An efficient greener copper triflate-catalyzed C-3 benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarin and some active methylene compounds

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Abstract : 4-Hydroxycoumarin has been directly benzylated at C-3 position with a good number of secondary benzylic alcohols using copper triflate catalyst (2 mol%) in toluene under reflux. The protocol provides an efficient, expedient and atom-economic access to warfarin and coumatetralyl analogues with potential anticoagulant activity. The protocol has been extended to benzylation of 4-hydroxy-1-methylquinolin-2(1H)-1-one, N-methylbarbiturate and some other active methylene compounds with remarkable success.

Keywords : 4-Hydroxycoumarin, secondary benzylic alcohols, alkylation, copper triflate, warfarin analogues.

Introduction

3-Benzylated-4-hydroxycoumarin framework is often encountered as a key structural motif in a wide range of bioactive compounds and synthetic intermediates that can be elaborated into molecules of pharmaceutical interest¹. 3-Benzylated-4-hydroxycoumarins such as warfarin, coumatetralyl are particularly important as clotting inhibitors for treatment of thrombosis². Bromadiolone and brodifacoum are utilized in drug development as they serve as scaffolds for further synthetic diversification into bioactive 3,4-disubstituted derivatives³.

The existing methods of C-3 alkylation/benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarins employ organic halides, acetates, carboxylates, phosphonates or boronic acids as alkyl/benzyl source under basic or Pd-catalyzed conditions⁴. Most of these methods are stoichiometric, atom uneconomic, generate substantial amounts of salts as waste products and require handling of toxic materials. Therefore, there is a need to develop a greener catalytic method for C-3 benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarins. Direct alkylation of 4-hydroxycoumarins utilizing alcohols as alkyl source represents a potential atom- and step-economic approach as water is the only byproduct of the reaction. However, hydroxy group is a poor leaving group and to realize this objective in practice, it requires activation by an electrophile. Previously, 4-hydroxycoumarins were alkylated at C-3 position using stoichiometric amounts of strong

Brönsted acids⁵ under rather harsh conditions. Contemporary emphasis on development of environmentally friendly catalytic methods based on alcohols as pro-electrophiles led to the use of solid-supported acid Amberlite IR-120 (H⁺-form)⁶, molecular iodine⁷, iridium⁸ under solvent-free conditions. Use of trivalent metal triflates as hard Lewis acid catalysts has received considerable current attention for carbon-carbon bond formation reactions due to their efficacy, mildness and air-tolerant nature⁹. Recently, copper triflate has been utilized as a ligand-free source of copper catalysis. It has several advantageous features such as environment friendly nature, cost compatibility and ability to activate enolic -OH under mild conditions¹⁰. Copper triflate-catalyzed reactions do not require rigid exclusion of moisture or inert atmosphere conditions¹¹. In our continuing efforts to develop greener mild Lewis acid-catalyzed synthetic protocols¹² and encouraged by the report of copper triflate-catalyzed generation of propargylic cation from propargylic alcohols *en route* to tandem cycloisomerization to furans from 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds and enoxysilanes¹³, we ventured to evaluate hitherto unexplored efficacy of copper triflate as a catalyst for C-3 benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarin using secondary benzyl alcohols as the source of benzyl moiety. Herein, we disclose the results of a simple, straightforward and cost-effective procedure of Cu(OTf)₂-catalyzed C-3 benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarin employing π -activated secondary benzylic alcohols.

Results and discussion

We chose benzhydrol (**2a**) as a representative of activated secondary benzylic alcohols and carried out Cu(OTf)₂-catalyzed benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1a**) with it under various conditions. A number of polar and non-polar solvents such as toluene, dichloroethane, nitromethane, acetonitrile, dimethylformamide (DMF) and acetone were screened for their suitability as reaction medium. The catalytic performance of copper triflate was found to be markedly dependent upon the nature of solvent used. It was particularly effective in non-coordinating solvents, both polar and non-polar, such as toluene, dichloroethane and nitromethane. In contrast, DMF and acetonitrile gave poorer results presumably due to deactivation of Cu^{II} catalyst. Toluene was preferred to the halogenated solvent dichloroethane due to its better environmental acceptability. The C-3 benzylated product **3a** was obtained in an excellent yield of 96% with an optimal catalyst load of 2 mol% of Cu(OTf)₂ in toluene under reflux for 1 h (Table 1, entry 2). Notably, it was possible to carry out the reaction with a lower catalyst load of 1% in an acceptable yield of 85% but at the cost of longer reaction time (entry 1, Table 1).

Table 1. Optimization experiments on benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1a**) with benzhydrol (**2a**) with Cu(OTf)₂ catalyst

Entry	Cu(OTf) ₂ (mol%)	Solvent ^a	Reaction time (h)	Yield ^b (%)
1	1	Toluene	3	85
2	2	Toluene	1	96
3	2	Dichloroethane	1	92
4	2	Nitromethane	1	90
5	2	Acetonitrile	1	65
6	2	Acetone	3	10
7	2	DMF	3	70

^aReaction conditions : **1a** and **2a** in 1 mmol level each, solvent (4 mL/mmol of **1a**), reflux.

^bRefers to isolated yields upon column chromatography.

To demonstrate the generality and functional group compatibility of the method, a good number of secondary benzylic alcohols were reacted with 4-hydroxycoumarin

under optimized condition with success. The results are exhibited in Table 2.

Benzylation was particularly fast and high-yielding for the benzhydrol substituted with 4-allyloxy moiety (entry 2). Surprisingly, **3b** was formed in higher yield and shorter reaction time in toluene (98%, 10 min) rather than in nitromethane, although the latter should be supportive of the dibenzylmethyl cation formation due to its polar nature. The favourable solubility of **2b** in toluene due to its lipophilic nature seems to be compatible with this observation. *p*-Toluenesulfonic acid-catalyzed benzylation of 1,3-dicarbonyl compounds with 1-phenylethanol (**2c**) in dichloromethane under reflux¹⁴ has been reported to yield 1,3-diphenylbut-1-ene as a byproduct by way of competitive elimination and dimerization. Gratifyingly, no such undesirable product was formed when **2c** or its derivatives were subjected to alkylation under optimized condition of the present method. It was also evident that benzylation could be only accomplished with secondary benzylic alcohols but not with primary benzylic, nonbenzylic propargyl or allyl alcohol (entries 18–20). The reaction with the benzyl alcohol **2n** was a failure even after prolonged exposure due to its deactivation by the of benzoyl moiety (entry 21). Alkylation reaction was also clean and efficient with 1-(thiophen-2-yl)ethanol (entry 11). Sterically hindered 7-isopropyl tetrahydronaphthalene-1-ol gave coumatetralyl analogue **3j**, albeit in somewhat lower yield of 60% (entry 13). The method was successfully extended to benzylation of 4-hydroxy-1-methylquinolin-2(1*H*)-1-one, *N*-methylbarbiturate, 1*H*-indene-1, 3(2*H*)-dione and malononitrile (entries 12–16). Previously, 5-benzylation of barbiturate was carried out with diarylmethyl cation in the presence of an excess of BF₃·OEt₂/SnCl₄ in glacial acetic acid¹⁵ at reflux temperature but the yields were rather low.

The catalytic action of Cu(OTf)₂ is primarily due to its ability to activate the donor component, 4-hydroxycoumarin by way of formation of copper enolate. This also releases strong triflic acid (TfOH), (H₀ value -14.1)¹⁶ with potential to activate the benzylic alcohol towards generation of carbocation intermediate. Thus Cu(OTf)₂ acts as a mild Lewis acid activator as well as a tunable source of Brønsted acid for electrophilic activation of the alcohol component. Significantly, appreciable enol content of the active methylene compound is crucial for suc-

Table 2. Cu(OTf)₂-catalyzed benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarin and other active methylene compounds with secondary alcohols

Entry	Nucleophile	Alcohol	Product ^a	Time	Yield ^b (%)
1		1 h	96		
2	1a		(i) 10 min (ii) 1 h	98 86 ^c	
3	1a		2 h	82	
4	1a		1.5 h	88	
5	1a		1 h	80	
6	1a		1.5 h	86	
7	1a		1.5 h	80	
8	1a		50 min	93	
9	1a		1 h	90	
10	1a		1.5 h	60	
11	1a		2.5 h	82	
12		1 h	70		

Table-2 (contd.)

13		1 h	60		
14		1.5 h	89		
15		1.5 h	75		
16		1.5 h	55		
17		2.5 h	70		
18	1a		N.R.	6 h	-
19	1a		N.R.	18 h	-
20	1a		N.R.	10 h	-
21	1a		N.R.	6 h	-
22		N.R.	6 h	-	
23		N.R.	6 h	-	

^aAll products were characterized by ¹H, ¹³C NMR and mass spectroscopy.

^bRefers to isolated yield after column chromatography.

^cTime and yield of **3b** refers to the reaction in nitromethane under reflux.

cess of the method. Failure of alkylation of an active methylene compound such as diethyl malonate (entry 23) with little enol content supports this view. Water released during alkylation may further generate TfOH ($pK_1 = 7.3$ for Cu^{2+})¹⁷ from hydrolyzable $\text{Cu}(\text{OTf})_2$. It is reasonable to assume that TfOH may be the real catalyst with its copper(II) salt merely acting as a precatalyst. To test this hypothesis concerning the catalytic role of TfOH, a control experiment was performed by exposing 4-

hydroxycoumarin to 1-(4-chlorophenyl)ethanol (**2g**) in the presence of 2 mol% TfOH in refluxing toluene for 1.5 h. In contrast to the $\text{Cu}(\text{OTf})_2$ -catalyzed benzylation that exclusively affords **3g** in 80% yield (entry 7, Table 2), it was isolated in a much lower yield of 68% together with some unidentified byproducts (Scheme 1). This result clearly showed that copper triflate was a superior and milder catalyst than triflic acid. Notably, TfOH has been also found to be an unsatisfactory catalyst for addition of

β -dicarbonyl compounds to alcohol¹⁸ under homogeneous conditions. A separate exploratory experiment was designed for alkylation of **1a** with **2g** using $\text{Cu}(\text{OTf})_2$ -catalyst together with potassium carbonate with the aim to delink Lewis acid catalysis of oxophilic Cu^{II} from proton catalysis (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

It was reasoned that the mild base potassium carbonate would eliminate proton catalysis by neutralizing TfOH without hindering Cu^{II} catalysis due to weak interaction with Cu^{II} with carbonate ligand. The reaction yielded **3g** but in a much lower yield of 60% compared to the same reaction under optimized conditions (entry 7, Table 2). This demonstrated that Cu^{II} was essential to the efficacy of the reaction although triflic acid certainly cooperated with its Cu^{II} salt to help attainment of higher yield of benzylated product within short reaction time and that, too, with a low catalyst load of 2 mol%. However, TfOH played a decisive role in product formation for substrates with acid-labile moieties such as Meldrum's acid. Alkylation of Meldrum's acid with benzhydrol afforded 3,3-diphenylpropanoic acid (**3r**) instead of the expected dibenzylated product **3q**. Formation of **3r** may be explained by hydrolytic cleavage of the acid-labile bislactone moiety of the benzylated product via ketene formation. Analogous mechanistic scenario prevailed in the proline-promoted condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarin with Meldrum's acid and benzaldehyde¹⁹ (Scheme 2).

A tentative catalytic cycle involved in the benzylation of **1a** is shown in Scheme 3.

Our success in C-3 benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarin opens up the possibility of heterocyclization in case of 3-allylated derivatives of **1a** leading to one-pot synthesis of biologically relevant pyranocoumarins²⁰. This is particularly promising for pyranocoumarins bearing reactive io-

dine atom in the pyran ring with scope for further synthetic manipulation by way of C-C bond formation via metalation. Treatment of **1a** with **2h** under usual alkylation conditions followed by treatment with I_2 - NaHCO_3 in aqueous acetonitrile at reflux temperature afforded the dihydropyranocoumarin, 2,4-diphenyl-3-iodo-2,3-

Scheme 2

dihydropyrano[3,2,*b*]benzo-1-pyran-5-one **4a** exclusively in an overall yield of 89% (Scheme 4).

Interestingly, the coupling pattern of hydrogen on the iodine-bearing C-3 of the dihydropyran ring (δ 5.45, dd, $J_{3a,2a}$ 8.4, $J_{3a,4e'}$ 4.8 Hz) flanked by an axial hydrogen on homoallylic C-2 adjacent to oxygen (δ 5.28, d, $J_{2a,3a}$ 8.4 Hz) and pseudoequatorial C-4 H (δ 4.66, d, $J_{4e',3a}$ 4.8 Hz) allows confirmation of its stereostructure as **4a**. The diastereoselectivity of the iodolactonization process is governed by the allylic 1, 2 ($A^{1,2}$) strain²¹ factor that favors pseudoaxial orientation of the sterically demanding C-4 phenyl of **4a** rather than its pseudoequatorial position.

We have developed a simple, cost-effective and efficient method for C-3 benzylation of 4-hydroxycoumarin

Scheme 3

Scheme 4

with secondary benzylic alcohols using a low catalyst load of copper triflate (2 mol%) in toluene under refluxing conditions. High yield, short reaction time, operational simplicity and its scope of extension to other active methylene compounds are attractive features of the protocol.

Experimental

Representative procedure for preparation of 3-[1-(4-allyloxyphenyl)ethyl]-4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one (3d):

To a solution of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1a**) (186 mg, 1.15 mmol) in toluene (4 ml) were sequentially added copper triflate (9 mg, 0.025 mmol) and 1-(4-allyloxyphenyl)ethanol (**2d**) (207 mg, 1.16 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1.5 h when TLC monitoring showed complete disappearance of the starting materials. The residue remaining after removal of solvent under vacuum was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 5 mL) and the combined extract was dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Concentration of dried extract and column chromatogra-

phy over silica gel (60–120 mesh) using light petrol-ethyl acetate (2 : 1) as eluent afforded **3d** (325 mg, 88%) as a white solid, m.p. 140–142 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3323, 1671, 1624, 1609, 1509, 1447, 1421, 1393, 1241, 1221, 1177, 1119, 1018, 925, 879, 833, 755 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.65 (1H, dd, *J* 7.6, 1.2 Hz), 7.53–7.48 (1H, m), 7.40 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.32–7.20 (2H, m), 6.98 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 6.12 (1H, s), 6.10–6.01 (1H, m), 5.43 (1H, dd, *J* 15.6, 1.6 Hz), 5.31 (1H, dd, *J* 10.8, 1.6 Hz), 4.65 (1H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz), 4.55 (2H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 1.63 (3H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 163.5, 159.7, 158.2, 152.4, 133.0, 132.9, 131.8, 128.4, 123.8, 122.8, 117.9, 116.3, 116.1, 115.9, 110.0, 68.8, 33.8, 16.7 ppm; MS (ESI⁺) : *m/z* 323 [M+1]⁺.

*Typical procedure for one-pot synthesis of substituted pyranocoumarin, 2,4-diphenyl-3-iodo-2,3-dihydropyrano-[3,2-*b*]benzo-1-pyran-5-one (4a):*

To a solution of 4-hydroxycoumarin (**1a**) (192 mg,

1.18 mmol) in toluene (4 mL) was added Cu(OTf)₂ (0.023 mmol, 8.5 mg). This was followed by addition of 1,3-diphenylprop-2-en-1-ol (**2h**) (248 mg, 1.18 mmol) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h when TLC monitoring showed complete disappearance of the starting material **1a**. A solution of pulverized iodine (3.3 mmol, 416 mg) in CH₃CN-H₂O (2 : 1, 4 mL) was added to the mixture followed by the addition of NaHCO₃ (6 mmol, 500 mg) and the mixture was refluxed for 1 h. After completion of the reaction, organic solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the residue was extracted with ethyl acetate (3 × 7 mL). The combined extract was washed with a saturated solution of Na₂S₂O₃ (2 mL) and water. The dried extract (Na₂SO₄) was then concentrated and subjected to column chromatography over silica gel (60–120 mesh) using light petrol-ethyl acetate (20 : 1) as eluent to afford the pyranocoumarin **4a** (504 mg, 89%) exclusively as white solid, m.p. 186–188 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 1722, 1647, 1494, 1405, 1037, 901, 760 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.59–7.55 (2H, m), 7.45 (2H, m), 7.39–7.27 (10H, m), 5.45 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4, 4.8 Hz), 5.28 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 4.66 (1H, d, *J* 4.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 165.5, 159.5, 155.3, 140.1, 138.8, 132.8, 129.1, 128.8, 128.7, 128.5, 127.8, 127.5, 124.1, 122.9, 117.0, 112.2, 105.5, 96.9, 51.3, 32.6 ppm; MS (ESI⁺) : *m/z* 481 [M+1]⁺.

Selected characterization data :

3-[(4-Allyloxyphenyl)(phenyl)methyl]-4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one (3b, Table 2) : Viscous yellow liquid; IR (KBr) : ν 3397, 3083, 1668, 1624, 1609, 1508, 1495, 1454, 1387, 1243, 1179, 1108, 998, 898, 756 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.73 (1H, dd, *J* 8.0, 1.2 Hz), 7.56–7.51 (1H, m), 7.40–7.24 (7H, m), 7.17 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 6.92 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 6.31 (1H, bs), 6.09–6.00 (1H, m), 5.90 (1H, s), 5.41 (1H, dd, *J* 17.2, 1.2 Hz), 5.29 (1H, dd, *J* 10.4, 0.8 Hz), 4.53 (2H, d, *J* 5.2 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 163.3, 160.7, 158.1, 152.7, 140.3, 133.0, 132.1, 131.9, 129.9, 129.3, 128.7, 127.6, 123.9, 123.1, 117.9, 116.4, 116.0, 115.6, 107.9, 68.8, 46.5 ppm; MS (ESI⁺) : *m/z* 385 [M+1]⁺.

3-[1-(4-Chlorophenyl)ethyl]-4-hydroxy-2H-chromen-2-one (3g, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 175–177 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3085, 1675, 1661, 1604, 1557, 1493, 1461,

1417, 1371, 1204, 1150, 1010, 963, 832, 755 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.68 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.53 (1H, t, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.43–7.38 (4H, m), 7.32–7.23 (2H, m), 4.69 (1H, q, *J* 7.6 Hz), 1.66 (3H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 163.4, 159.8, 152.4, 140.3, 133.4, 132.0, 129.5, 128.7, 124.0, 122.8, 116.4, 115.8, 109.6, 33.9, 16.6 ppm; MS (ESI⁺) : *m/z* 301 [M+1]⁺.

1-(3-Chlorophenyl)-3-phenyl-3-(4-hydroxy-2-oxo-2H-chromenyl)-1-propene (3i, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 167–169 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3026, 1668, 1609, 1568, 1495, 1390, 1216, 1104, 972, 756, 698 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.78 (1H, dd, *J* 8.8, 1.6 Hz), 7.59–7.55 (1H, m), 7.42–7.28 (11H, m), 6.75 (1H, dd, *J* 16.0, 6.0 Hz), 6.49 (1H, d, *J* 16.0 Hz), 5.43 (1H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 162.9, 161.1, 152.7, 141.6, 135.0, 134.7, 132.4, 130.8, 129.5, 128.7, 128.4, 128.2, 128.0, 127.8, 126.6, 126.3, 124.1, 123.1, 116.6, 115.7, 105.7, 43.9 ppm; MS (ESI⁺) : *m/z* 389 [M+1]⁺.

4-Hydroxy-3-(7-isopropyl-1,2,3,4-tetrahydronaphthalen-1-yl)-2H-chromen-2-one (3j, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 158–160 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 2958, 1680, 1655, 1619, 1565, 1495, 1448, 1386, 1281, 1220, 1188, 1105, 1090, 949, 814, 758 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.67 (1H, dd, *J* 7.6, 1.4 Hz), 7.52 (1H, td, *J* 8.0, 1.4 Hz), 7.33 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.25–7.10 (4H, m), 4.58 (1H, t, *J* 6.4 Hz), 2.88 (2H, d, *J* 4.0 Hz), 2.83–2.76 (1H, m), 2.42–2.17 (1H, m), 1.94–1.83 (3H, m), 1.17 (3H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz), 1.14 (3H, d, *J* 6.4 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 163.7, 160.2, 152.5, 148.2, 135.3, 134.4, 131.7, 130.5, 127.5, 126.1, 123.8, 123.0, 116.3, 109.2, 36.5, 33.6, 29.4, 23.9, 23.8, 21.6 ppm; MS (ESI⁺) : *m/z* 335 [M+1]⁺.

4-Hydroxy-3-[1-(thiophen-2-yl)ethyl]-2H-chromen-2-one (3k, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 196–198 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3229, 1673, 1627, 1390, 1210, 1165, 877, 755 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 7.71 (1H, dd, *J* 8.0, 1.6 Hz), 7.55–7.50 (1H, m), 7.38 (1H, d, *J* 5.2 Hz), 7.31 (1H, dd, *J* 8.4, 0.8 Hz), 7.26–7.22 (1H, m), 7.19–7.17 (1H, m), 7.06 (1H, dd, *J* 5.2, 3.6 Hz), 6.52 (1H, bs), 4.85 (1H, q, *J* 7.2 Hz), 1.73 (3H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 162.9, 160.5, 152.5, 146.4, 132.0, 127.2, 127.0, 124.8, 123.9, 123.0, 116.4, 116.0, 109.1, 31.3, 18.5 ppm; MS (ESI⁺) : *m/z* 273 [M+1]⁺.

3-Benzhydryl-4-hydroxy-1-methylquinolin-2(1H)-one (3l, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 166–168 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3438, 3022, 1631, 1614, 1559, 1493, 1448, 1418, 1340, 1241, 1090, 1076, 1031, 982, 752 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.65 (1H, d, J 2.0 Hz), 7.35–7.21 (9H, m), 7.10 (4H, d, J 7.2 Hz), 5.81 (1H, s), 5.59 (1H, s), 3.68 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 163.1, 157.0, 143.5, 140.9, 137.5, 132.2, 129.3, 128.4, 127.4, 126.5, 123.8, 116.0, 113.9, 56.3, 47.3 ppm; MS (ESI^+) : m/z 342 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

3-[(4-Allyloxyphenyl)(phenyl)methyl]-4-hydroxy-1-methylquinolin 2(1H)-one (3m, Table 2) : Dense yellow liquid; IR (KBr) : ν 3431, 2924, 1633, 1609, 1580, 1508, 1462, 1391, 1242, 1178, 1024, 997, 832, 756 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.89 (1H, dd, J 8.0, 1.2 Hz), 7.56 (1H, td, J 8.0, 1.2 Hz), 7.36–7.19 (7H, m), 7.17 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 6.99 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 6.18 (1H, s), 6.09–6.02 (1H, m), 5.40 (1H, dd, J 17.2, 1.6 Hz), 5.28 (1H, dd, J 10.4, 1.2 Hz), 4.51 (2H, d, J 5.2 Hz), 3.70 (3H, s); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 163.2, 157.9, 157.1, 141.2, 139.1, 133.1, 132.9, 130.8, 129.2, 128.8, 127.3, 123.5, 121.6, 117.8, 116.2, 115.4, 113.7, 113.6, 68.8, 46.5, 29.7 ppm; MS (ESI^+) : m/z 398 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

5-Benzhydryl-1,3-dimethylpyrimidine-2,4,6-(1H,3H,5H)-trione (3n, Table 2) : Light brown solid, m.p. 158–160 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3027, 2957, 1741, 1667, 1447, 1427, 1375, 1267, 1238, 1112, 1034, 997, 885, 789 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.33–7.25 (10H, m) 4.96 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz), 4.42 (1H, d, J 2.8 Hz), 3.08 (6H, s); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 168.0, 150.9, 138.9, 129.3, 128.6, 128.4, 127.6, 55.2, 53.6, 28.3 ppm; MS (ESI^+) : m/z 323 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

2-Benzhydryl-1H-indene-1,3-(2H)-dione (3o, Table 2) : Yellow solid, m.p. 110–112 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 1743, 1708, 1591, 1450, 1351, 1255, 751 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.86 (2H, dd, J 5.6, 3.2 Hz), 7.74 (2H, dd, J 5.6, 3.2 Hz), 7.32 (4H, d, J 7.6 Hz), 7.21 (4H, td, J 6.8, 1.6 Hz), 7.16–7.12 (2H, m), 5.12 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz), 3.91 (1H, d, J 2.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 199.4, 142.5, 141.0, 135.5, 129.0, 128.2, 126.7, 123.1, 58.0, 49.9 ppm; MS (ESI^+) : m/z 313 $[\text{M}+1]^+$.

2-Benzhydrylmalononitrile (3p, Table 2) : Colorless liquid; IR (KBr) : ν 3064, 3032, 2910, 2256, 1497, 1453, 1103, 1083, 1032, 753 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.40–7.19 (10H, m), 4.62 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 4.40 (1H, d, J 8.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 137.0, 128.6, 128.4, 127.8, 111.9, 51.5, 29.0 ppm; MS (ESI^+) : m/z 231 $[\text{M}-1]^-$.

3,3-Diphenylpropanoic acid (3r, Table 2) : White solid, m.p. 152–154 °C; IR (KBr) : ν 3027, 1698, 1597, 1494, 1451, 1428, 1279, 1217, 1051, 920, 794 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.29–7.17 (10H, m), 4.52 (1H, t, J 8.0 Hz), 3.08 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 178.0, 143.2, 128.6, 127.6, 126.6, 46.6, 40.4 ppm; MS (ESI^+) : m/z 249 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}]^+$.

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